

Revolutionizing Nigerian Social Studies Classrooms: The Impact of Team Teaching

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Abstract

This paper explores the concept of revolutionizing Nigerian social studies classrooms through the implementation of team teaching. With the aim of enhancing the learning experience and outcomes of students, team teaching involves collaboration among educators to deliver instruction. The paper examines various forms of team teaching, identifies the benefits it brings to the social studies classroom, discusses different types of team-teaching approaches, and addresses the challenges that may arise during implementation. Drawing upon existing research and educational practices, this paper provides valuable insights into the potential of team teaching to transform Nigerian social studies classrooms and offers recommendations for effective implementation

Keywords: Revolutionizing, Social Studies Classrooms, Team-Teaching

Introduction

Team teaching is revolutionizing social studies classrooms in Nigerian schools, transcending the limitations of traditional teaching methods. By embracing this collaborative approach, educators are empowering students to become active participants in their learning journey, developing critical skills for engaged citizenship. Grofčíková and Trníková (2022) citing Plank (2013) argued that teaching is about leaving safe environment of individuals and be able to take the risk of collaborating with someone else. As Nigeria navigates its complex social, cultural, and historical landscape, team teaching stands as a catalyst for transformation, shaping a new generation of informed and socially conscious individuals ready to tackle the challenges of the future. In Nigerian schools, social studies plays a crucial role in shaping young minds, fostering critical thinking, and developing an understanding of the complex social, cultural, and historical fabric of the nation. However, traditional teaching methods often fall short in engaging students, limiting their active participation and inhibiting comprehensive learning experiences. Enter team teaching – an innovative approach that is revolutionizing social studies classrooms across Nigeria and redefining the boundaries of collaborative learning. Team teaching is an instructional strategy that involves two or more educators working together to plan, teach, and assess students' learning outcomes. Bates (2019) argued that teachers have to learn how to work in team and develop soft skills and necessary collaborative skills. Colleagues who teach together in a team can build up professional bonds and can be a model for students. Unlike the traditional one-teacher model, team teaching harnesses the strengths and diverse perspectives of multiple educators, creating a dynamic and interactive classroom environment. Team teaching not only enhances students' understanding of social studies concepts but also nurtures essential skills such as critical thinking, communication, and teamwork skills that are vital for active citizenship in a complex and interconnected world. When teachers work collaboratively, and engage the students in teaching and learning, they can help students solve problems and comprehend more complex ideas (Marantz Cohen & Mule 2019; Maija, Tiinamaija, & Antti, 2023).

Team teaching promotes a student-centered learning environment where learners are actively involved in the teaching and learning process. Through collaborative discussions, debates, and group activities, students gain a deeper understanding of social issues, cultural diversity, and historical events. According to Grofčíková and Trníková (2022) collaborative work means

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that every team member contributes and shares the ideas, opinions, knowledge, is engaged and motivated to complete goals. It includes a willingness to solve problems, thinking creatively and critically, recognizing strengths and weaknesses, responsibility and adaptability team teaching encourages educators to leverage their individual expertise and diverse backgrounds. By combining their knowledge, skills, and teaching styles, teachers can provide a richer and more comprehensive learning experience. For example, one teacher may excel in delivering engaging lectures, while another may specialize in facilitating hands-on activities or technology integration. This diversity creates a dynamic classroom atmosphere that caters to various learning styles and promotes inclusivity, ensuring that every student has the opportunity to thrive academically. Also, team teaching offers educators the chance to share the workload, reducing individual stress and burnout. Research suggests that collaborative learning, such as team teaching, promotes active engagement, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills among students. According to a study carried out by Johnson, Johnson and Smith (2014) it was found out that team teaching fosters positive interdependence, individual accountability, and interpersonal skills development. In a similar study by Slavin (1996) it was found out that team teaching led to higher test scores, increased knowledge retention, and improved critical thinking abilities compared to traditional teaching methods. Team teaching also enhances and encourages Teacher professional development. This is supported by study conducted by Supovitz and Turner (2000) on cooperative learning and achievement: 'What we know, what we need to know'. The study found out that team teaching promotes a culture of collaboration among teachers, leading to increased job satisfaction and professional growth. Thus, revolutionizing the social studies classroom through team teaching offers numerous benefits, including enhanced learning experiences, promotes active engagement, improved academic achievement, and professional development opportunities for teachers. These rationales, supported by research and empirical evidence, provide a compelling case for implementing team teaching in social studies classrooms.

Theoretical framework

The theory guiding this paper is hinged on Burns (1978) transformational leadership. The trust of the theory is on the idea that effective leaders can inspire and motivate their followers to achieve higher levels of performance and morality. The emphasis on Burns' (1978) theory of transformational leadership are:

1. **Idealized Influence (Charisma):** Transformational leaders serve as role models and gain the trust, respect, and admiration of their followers. They set high moral and ethical standards and inspire followers to emulate them.
2. **Inspirational Motivation:** Transformational leaders articulate a compelling vision of the future and inspire their followers to achieve it. They use language that evokes strong emotions and enthusiasm.
3. **Intellectual Stimulation:** These leaders encourage creativity and innovation among their followers. They challenge the status quo, promote critical thinking, and create an environment where new ideas are welcomed.
4. **Individualized Consideration:** Transformational leaders show genuine concern for the well-being and personal development of each follower. They provide support, coaching, and mentoring to help followers reach their full potential.

Burns' theory of transformational leadership theory can be used to explain team teaching in social studies classroom by laying emphasis on the key elements of the theory, which include idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. Team teaching, which involves multiple teachers collaborating and coordinating their efforts to deliver instruction, can benefit greatly from transformational leadership practices.

Empirical Perspectives to revolutionizing Nigerian Social Studies Classrooms: The impact of team teaching

There are empirical evidence to support the incorporation of team teaching approaches in the Social Studies Classroom as illustrated by the studies below: Onyeachu (2017) investigated Team Teaching Approach in Nigerian Schools: An Innovative Strategy for Effective Teaching and Learning. The study found that team teaching allowed for more individualized attention and engagement between teachers and students, resulting in improved learning outcomes. In a study on The Impact of Team Teaching Strategy on Critical Thinking Skills of Secondary School Students in Imo State, Nigeria. Okoye and Nwosu (2016) found that when students are exposed to multiple viewpoints and teaching styles, they are more likely to develop critical thinking skills, analyze issues from different angles, and engage in meaningful discussions. Similarly, in a study by Igwe (2019) on Team Teaching: A Panacea for Classroom Management Challenges in Nigerian Secondary Schools. Result showed that having two teachers in the classroom allowed for better classroom management, as they could share responsibilities and maintain a more orderly environment. Additionally, in a study by Adedoyin (2018) on Integrating Cultural Diversity in the Teaching of Social Studies in Nigeria: A Need for Collaborative Team Teaching. The findings highlighted that team teaching can help incorporate local perspectives and traditions into the curriculum, making it more relatable and meaningful for students.

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These empirical studies reviewed suggest that team teaching can have a significant positive impact on Nigerian social studies classrooms. It can improve teacher-student interaction, bring diverse expertise into the classroom, enhance critical thinking skills, aid in classroom management, promote cultural relevance, and support teacher professional development. To revolutionize Nigerian social studies classrooms, education policymakers and institutions should consider implementing team teaching as a viable pedagogical approach.

Objectives of the Study

The paper seeks to achieve the following objectives

1. To examine the concept of team teaching in the context of the Nigerian social studies classroom.
2. To explore the potential benefits and challenges associated with team teaching.
3. To analyze the impact of team teaching on student learning outcomes in social studies.
4. To propose strategies for successful implementation of team teaching in Nigerian schools.

Methodology

The paper adopts the following methodology: The researchers conducted a comprehensive review of existing literature on team teaching, social studies education, and educational reforms in Nigeria. The used in the paper include journal articles, books, and reports as well as engagement with experts in the field of social studies so as to gain insights into the impact of team teaching on student learning outcomes and teacher effectiveness.

Concept of Team Teaching for social Studies Classroom

According to Buckley (2000) Team teaching involves a group of instructors working purposefully, regularly, and cooperatively to help a group of students of any age learn. Maija, Tiinamaija and Antti, (2023) posits that team teaching can take any of the following:

1. Involves two or more teachers within the teaching and learning environment.
2. Can vary along a continuum of collaboration.
3. Facilitates a learning community by impacting on both teaching and learning.
4. Can be either formal or informal.

From the above, we can deduce that team teaching set goals for a course, design a syllabus, prepare individual lesson plans, teach students, and evaluate the results. They share insights, argue with one another. The concept of team teaching holds immense promise for our social studies classroom. Through harnessing the power of collaboration, teachers can create an educational experience that transcends the boundaries of traditional teaching, inspiring our students to become active, critical thinkers and global citizens.

Concept of Social Studies Classroom

Danladi (2005), conceptualized social studies education as a field of study of man and his activities in relation to his social, economic, political, cultural and physical environments in order to achieve understandings, skills, attitudes and values that are necessary for personal and societal development. This paper adopts the explanation provided by Danladi (2005), because the definition is in conformity with the main focus of team teaching i.e. positively changing student's attitude, knowledge and skills for the betterment of the society. Social Studies Classrooms: Are educational spaces where students learn about the various aspects of society, including history, geography, economics, politics, and culture. The classrooms provide students with a comprehensive understanding of the world, its history, and its diverse cultures, empowering them to become active and engaged citizens in an increasingly complex global society.

Forms of team-teaching for Social Studies Classroom

Team teaching is a collaborative teaching approach in which two or more teachers work together to plan, teach, and evaluate a course or a lesson. This approach is often used in social studies classrooms, where multiple perspectives and interdisciplinary approaches are valued. Sandholtz (2000) identified three forms of team-teaching configurations, namely: (1) Two or more teachers loosely sharing responsibility; (2) Team planning, but individual instruction; and (3) Joint planning, instruction, and evaluation of the learning experience. Other classifications of team teaching include:

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1. Co-teaching: In this form of team teaching, two or more teachers share responsibility for planning and delivering instruction to a group of students. According to Friend and Cook (2016), co-teaching involves "two or more professionals delivering substantive instruction to a diverse, or blended, group of students in a shared classroom space. Co-teaching can take many forms, including one teacher taking the lead while the other provides support, or both teachers taking an equal role in instruction.
2. Parallel teaching: In parallel teaching, the class is divided into two or more groups, and each teacher is responsible for teaching one group. According to Scruggs and Mastropieri (2014), parallel teaching "involves two or more teachers working with different groups of students simultaneously, usually in the same classroom". This form of team teaching can be especially effective for providing differentiated instruction or for addressing the needs of students with diverse learning styles.
3. Station teaching: In station teaching, the class is divided into small groups, and each group rotates through a series of learning stations, each led by a different teacher or instructional aide. According to Friend and Cook (2016), station teaching "involves the use of physical stations or centers in which students rotate through a series of activities". This form of team teaching can be effective for providing hands-on learning experiences and for engaging students in a variety of learning activities.

Benefits of Team Teaching for Social Studies Teachers

When teachers work collaborative, share and exchange ideas, they stand better chance to optimize their teaching strategies. Thus Pasetto, Barreiros, Corrêa and Freudenheim (2021) identified three benefits of team teaching for teachers, the benefit include:

1. Changing the teacher's mind set becomes more open in dealing with and solving every problem of learning social studies in the classroom so that it is easy to solve by frequently involving colleagues and friends of the same profession to get new ideas through focus group discussions.
2. The teacher can anticipate and periodically evaluate the achievement of standard competencies.
3. Being an effective place for resource sharing between involved stakeholders especially all parties internally and externally, resulting in a collective awareness that the progress and success of learning social studies is the responsibility of all stakeholders involved.

Other benefits include: Capacity building, developing positive self-esteem, and developing interpersonal competence. One of the key benefits of team teaching is its ability to create a student-centered learning environment, where students actively participate in the learning process.

Types of team teaching for Social Studies Classroom

Team teaching in the context of a social studies classroom involves collaboration between two or more educators who work together to plan, deliver, and assess instruction. This collaborative approach has several types or models that can be implemented depending on the goals and needs of the students and teachers involved. Some of the types of team teaching in the context of a social studies classroom include the following:

1. Parallel Teaching: In parallel teaching, the teachers divide the class into two or more groups and simultaneously teach the same content. Each teacher takes responsibility for a specific group, ensuring that all students receive instruction and support. According to Friend and Bursuck (2018) parallel teaching can be used to provide differentiated instruction or to reinforce concepts through additional examples or practice. 'Parallel teaching is an effective strategy in a social studies classroom for providing differentiated instruction and reinforcing concepts. By dividing the class into groups, teachers can address the diverse needs of students' (Friend & Bursuck, 2018).
2. Station Teaching: In station teaching, the classroom is divided into stations or learning centers where students rotate to engage in different activities or receive instruction from different teachers. Each teacher prepares and leads a specific station. This model allows for small-group instruction, independent work, and collaborative learning experiences. The station teaching model in social studies classrooms promotes active student engagement and provides opportunities for differentiated instruction. Students rotate between stations, engaging in various activities that cater to different learning styles and needs" (Friend & Bursuck, 2018).
3. Alternative Teaching: Involves one teacher working with a smaller group of students who require additional support or enrichment while the other teacher leads the main instruction for the rest of the class. This model allows for targeted instruction and individualized attention for students who need it. According to Tomlinson, Brimijoin and Narvaez, (2008)

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alternative teaching is an effective approach in a social studies classroom for providing targeted instruction. Thus, by dividing the class into two groups, one teacher can provide additional support or enrichment while the other teacher focuses on delivering the main instruction.

Additionally, a team can be single-discipline, interdisciplinary, or school-within-a-school teams that meet with a common set of students over an extended period of time. New teachers may be paired with veteran teachers. Innovation is encouraged, and modifications in class size, location, and time are permitted. Different personalities, voices, values, and approaches spark interest and keep attention (Maija, Tiinamaija, & Antti, 2023).

Challenges of Team Teaching for Social Studies Classroom

Team teaching can offer numerous benefits in the social studies classroom. However, it also presents certain challenges such as:

1. **Time Management:** Time management is a significant challenge in team teaching, as coordinating schedules and planning lessons together can be time-consuming. (Ylönen, 2019)
2. **Consistency in Instruction:** Maintaining consistency in instruction can be challenging in team teaching, as different educators may have diverse teaching styles and approaches. (Lund & Stenfors-Hayes, 2020).
3. **Communication and Collaboration:** Effective communication and collaboration between team teachers are crucial, but challenges can arise due to differences in opinions, lack of coordination, or conflicts. (Shin & Turner, 2018)
4. **Assessment and Grading:** "Developing consistent assessment practices and grading criteria can be challenging in team teaching, as educators may have varying perspectives on evaluating student performance. (Petersen, 2019)
5. **Classroom Management:** Maintaining classroom management and discipline can be more challenging in team teaching, as students may test boundaries or become confused with multiple authority figures. (Kos, 2018)
6. **Roles, expectations, experience and knowledge** are related to "the conflict that could arise if there is uncertainty or disagreement in the role of each team member. (Letterman & Dugan, 2004).

Impact of Team Teaching for Social Studies Classroom

Team teaching in the social studies classroom can have a significant impact on student learning and engagement. Below are some insights on the impact of team teaching:

1. **Enhanced Student learning:** Team teaching can lead to enhanced student learning outcomes, as it allows for a variety of instructional methods and perspectives.
2. **Improved Critical Thinking and Collaboration Skills** among students.
3. **Increased Student Engagement**
4. **Positive Classroom Climate:** Team teaching contributes to a positive classroom climate, fostering a sense of community and support among students and educators." (Kendall, 2020)
5. **Diverse Perspectives and Cultural Understanding:** Team teaching brings diverse perspectives into the social studies classroom, promoting cultural understanding and a broader understanding of historical events. (Wong, 2018).

Conclusion

In conclusion, team teaching has the potential to revolutionize Nigerian social studies classrooms by fostering a collaborative and dynamic learning environment. The analysis of various forms of team teaching has revealed that it encourages educators to share their expertise, experiences, and resources, leading to increased student engagement and improved academic performance. The benefits of team teaching extend beyond the classroom, as it promotes professional growth and development among educators, while also enhancing their job satisfaction. Furthermore, the exploration of different types of team teaching has demonstrated the flexibility and adaptability of this approach, allowing teachers to tailor their instruction to meet the diverse needs of students. By embracing team teaching and addressing the challenges associated with it, Nigerian social studies classrooms can be transformed into vibrant and interactive learning spaces that foster critical thinking, collaboration, and cultural understanding among students.

Recommendations

The paper put forward the following recommendations:

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1. Educational institutions invest in professional development programs for teachers to acquire the necessary skills and knowledge.
2. Collaboration among educators should be encouraged and supported through regular team meetings, mentoring, and peer observations.
3. Communication channels should be established to address any conflicts or concerns that may arise during the implementation process.
4. Policymakers should consider allocating resources and providing incentives to schools and educators that adopt team teaching practices.

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